

The Novelty Teaching Model for Socially Constructed Virtual COVID-19 Classrooms

Prof. Ahmad Al Yakin

Universitas Al Asyariah Mandar, Indonesia.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2756-5469>

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Abstract

Science and technology have made it possible for online education to become an integral part of today's education system. Although online education had some influence prior to the Covid 19 era, it has now become an essential part of higher education's teaching and learning process. Every government around the world was forced to incorporate online education into their higher education system after the Covid-19 imposed enormous challenges on the traditional higher education system. However, prior to the Covid-19, the Indonesian higher education sector did not place much emphasis on online education. The Covid-19 pandemic has a significant impact on the global education system. Public and private educational institutions across the country were temporarily shuttered to stem the tide of the virus's spread to stop it before it could do more harm. As a result, the educational activities of students around the world were severely disrupted. In addition to affecting students' education, the lockdown has had a significant impact on students' mental health. One estimate puts the number of students and young people affected by the closure of schools, universities, and other educational institutions at more than 1.5 billion. This article investigated the Novel Teaching Models for Socially Constructed Virtual Classrooms after COVID-19.

Keywords: Novelty, Teaching Methods, Social, Virtual Classrooms, Post COVID-19.

Introduction

During the era of work from home, most universities began their academic and administrative endeavors with the aid of technological devices and applications. Indonesia higher education sector has undergone a fundamental shift since the introduction of online education. Most university professors and administrators in Indonesia are unfamiliar with online education. In Indonesia universities, face-to-face teaching and learning has been used for a long time. As a result, breaking with tradition and conducting educational activities in an innovative online environment is viewed as a difficult one. Many universities have been reluctant to start online educational activities, and university teachers and administrators have also encountered difficulties in carrying out their responsibilities. They have been reluctant to launch online activities. Teachers, students, and other members of the school community who lack proficiency in modern technology have encountered several difficulties.

Literature Review

Pace, Pettit, & Barker, (2020) examined crisis learning, as opposed to the more commonplace digital learning scenarios, is more appropriate in the present context. New instructional methods and strategies are more important than ever for academic institutions to improve their curricula (Toquero, 2020). In addition to academic pursuits, educational institutions serve as hubs of social activity and interaction. Many children and young people will miss out on vital social interaction-based activities if educational programs are halted. Underprivileged children and young adults should be able to continue their education even if their schools are closed, making this a critical issue that must be addressed. Short-term academic institution closures due to emergencies are nothing new, but the current global scope and pace of educational instability are sadly unmatched and, if sustained, could cause psychological distress and misery at various levels (McCarthy, 2020).

Sociology's study of generation has only recently begun to gain traction. Even though Karl Mannheim's classic essay reignited a generation's interest, demographic, cultural, and intellectual developments have brought it back to life. Until now, the sociological literature has generally conceptualized a generation as a unit with a defined national boundary. Generational sociology must therefore create a theory about the global generation of people. This conceptual improvement is critical in light of the unprecedented ease with which traumatic events can now be felt on a global scale thanks to advances in global communication technology. Print media dominated the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, bringing people from all over the world together, while new broadcast technologies ushered in a transnational generation in the middle of the twentieth century. Late twentieth-century globalization, defined by electronic communication technologies and marked by an increase in interactivity, is different from earlier periods. First, the 1960s generation spawned the first global generation; now, with the rise of new electronic communications, there is greater potential for a generation that can communicate across national and time boundaries. If in the past historical trauma was combined with the opportunities available to create a national generation, now trauma experienced globally, facilitated by new media technologies, has the potential to create awareness of a global generation. Generational movements are increasingly shaped by the media. Being concerned with future generations rather than past ones makes this article speculative. Its goal is to spark debate and establish a new research agenda for the study of future generations, Edmunds, J., & Turner, B. S. (2005).

Onyido, J. A., & Nwaogu, O. A. (2022) society and the twenty-first century are in a constant state of flux. As a result of the rise of technology, the world has undergone a radical transformation. Throughout the 21st century, technology has become the norm, influencing all aspects of modern society and making it easier for people to communicate with each other. To say that technology hasn't impacted the educational sector would be an understatement. The introduction and use of technological gadgets and approaches in the educational process has had an impact on aspects of education such as distance learning and cognitive development, among others. Scholars have noted that students' educational performance has been impacted by the use of technological approaches to learning.

Discussion

Cyber evolution of the global Internet is the result of a worldwide technological breakthrough in the field of computer technology. Because of this, a new social phenomenon was born: the process of Cybersocialization of an individual. Cybersocialization has become increasingly popular among teenagers and young adults over the past decade, according to the results of empirical research.

Cybersocialization's impact on today's adolescents is examined using the socialization theory of Parsons and Merton, which states that a person adapts to cultural and other environmental factors. And according to A. Maslow and C. Rogers, socialization is a process of overcoming the negative influences of the environment and introducing one's own capabilities and abilities. Social experience, cultural values, and social norms must be learned by the younger generation in order to successfully integrate into society and achieve self-realization and self-actualization.

There has been a lot of attention paid to adolescents' socialization in the last decade, according to a theoretical review of the literature. Young people's socialization is characterized by a wide range of characteristics, according to three studies Sobkin V.S, (2008). They include changes in the environment, new socialization agents, and new socialization mechanisms, among other things. As a result, there are two types of socialization: primary and secondary. Primary socialization occurs when a student is younger and begins to explore the social world for the first time; secondary socialization occurs when an adult gains personal experience and the knowledge gained at a young age change through professional and creative activities.

In teaching the modern generation, it is important to be able to use technology effectively, but it is also important to have the ability to integrate technology into the classroom. The use of ICT is influenced by the knowledge of the lecturers in developing various teaching materials using applications and media according to the needs and characteristics of 21st century learners. Teaching and learning with ICT will be difficult for lecturers because they only have self-taught knowledge and skills in this field. In addition, lecturers need the ability to use ICT in ways that are specific to their roles as educators and students. The ability to apply pedagogical theory and principles to the use of ICT in the classroom is included in this competency. ICT competence is a prerequisite for using ICT so that learning can be interesting and build more harmonious social emotions.

Students' ICT proficiency and access to infrastructure are two new highlights, which not only confirm the validity of the existing framework but also augment it by incorporating previously unknown elements such as management support and classroom setting. When lecturers decide to use technology in their classrooms, they seek support, encouragement, and guidance from university management bodies (Gillies, 2016). It has been found that barriers to ICT use are most common in the arts and humanities, according to a recent study by Mercader and Gairin (2020).

In addition, lecturers consider their students' perspectives to be important in determining their use of ICT. Although the focus was on the use of ICT by lecturers and the

development of ICT-based teaching materials, lecturers emphasized the importance of considering the circumstances of the students. Educators will face a difficult task if students are not encouraged to use ICT in their education in an appropriate way. Like lecturers, students' use of ICT is influenced by the level of competence, attitudes, support, and availability of ICT infrastructure (Ali et al., 2018). Even though the main focus of novelty learning models and the importance of adapting to social changes, namely the use of ICT by lecturers, the ability to develop teaching materials, varied, creative and innovative learning instructions, in addition, lecturers are emphasized to consider the situation and needs of students. Lecturers will have difficulty integrating ICT into their teaching if students are not encouraged to use ICT in their education. Students, like instructors, need a certain level of competence, positive attitude, encouragement, and access to technology.

Findings

The use of ICT improves lecturers' ability to teach effectively. As found by Tella et al. (2007: 222), most teachers think ICT is very useful and makes teaching and learning easier, leading to their recommendation that "professional development policies should support ICT-related teaching models" and that "emphasis should be placed on the pedagogical foundation of the use of ICT" ICT for teaching and learning". In addition, lecturers' creativity is needed in creating a pleasant learning atmosphere.

Conclusion

In the absence of genuine software, adequate computers in the classroom, fast internet, adequate training, the latest ICT equipment not being available, expert technical support not being available, and a lack of administrative support, the officials of Indonesian schools and universities in rural area were unable to see the changes needed in education in the twenty-first century. In Indonesia, the use of ICT devices will not only revolutionize learning, but also the way teachers teach. Students' and lecturers' ability to develop creativity, communication, and other critical thinking skills will be improved through an educational transformation facilitated by ICT. This is because ICT allows education to support, enhance, and optimize information delivery.

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